

chemicals tested can provide seed protection from BI over a fairly long period. That protection had little relationship to their direct fungitoxic effects. Although the protection varied from one experiment to another, cupric chloride, ferric chloride, cycloheximide, p-chloromercuribenzoate, and sodium malonate provided good control under different cropping conditions and in different seasons. The compounds seem to act by activating a host defense in susceptible varieties that helps to restrict the number of infections and to limit lesion size, thus preventing the heavy inoculum buildup essential for severe BI infection. □

Table 2. Effect of chemicals used for wet seed treatment on BI symptoms. Pandua, West Bengal, India.^a

Chemical ^b	Lesions/ tiller (no.)	Proportion of lesions of different size groups ^c				Mean disease index per tiller ^d
		L	M	S	VS	
Control (water)	30.8	57	10	10	23	20.5
Cupric chloride	4.8	36	17	15	32	2.2 (89.3)
Barium chloride	22.8	53	12	12	23	14.6 (28.8)
Mercuric chloride	17.5	53	19	8	20	11.5 (43.9)
Lithium sulfate	15.4	34	17	15	34	10.2 (50.3)
Cysteine	13.7	42	16	15	27	7.7 (62.4)
Thioglycollic acid	16.8	47	15	14	24	10.1 (50.7)
Sodium selenite	18.3	34	11	34	21	8.1 (60.5)
Sodium malonate	10.8	40	16	14	30	5.9 (71.1)
Cycloheximide	6.2	36	14	14	36	3.1 (84.9)
p-chloromercuribenzoate	5.3	32	13	10	45	2.8 (86.4)
LSD (P = 0.01)						7.7

^aData represent average of observations from 30 tillers (one each from 30 plants). ^bChemicals were used at 10⁻⁴ M, except lithium sulfate and cysteine at 10⁻³ M, sodium selenite at 10⁻⁵ M, and cycloheximide at 10⁻⁶ M. ^cLesion size: L = large, M = medium, S = small, VS = very small. ^dValues in parentheses indicate percentage reduction from control.

Effect of additional nitrogen on incidence of the kresek phase of bacterial blight (BB)

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BB severity increases with N level. But the effect of added N on initial BB stages is not known. We conducted a pot experiment to measure the effect

of N on kresek.

Highly susceptible AC360 seedlings were transplanted at 25 d into porcelain pots filled with 6 kg dry field soil, and grown initially with 60 kg N/ha. At tillering, when tillers started showing kresek symptoms, half the pots were supplied additional N at 120 kg/ha. Each treatment was replicated seven times.

At flowering, no significant difference in kresek incidence was found (see table). But at tillering, plants receiving additional N showed

high vigor and produced more kresek-free tillers. □

Incidence of kresek in plants supplied additional nitrogen. CRRI, India.

Treatment	Total tillers (no.)	Kresek tillers (no.)	Panicle- bearing tillers (no.)
60 kg N/ha (initial)	13.3	3.7	5.7
120 kg N/ha (additional)	25.6	3.4	15.3
CD 5%	1.9	ns ^a	2.7
1%	2.7		3.8

^aNot significant.

Blast (BI) outbreak in northeastern Haryana, India

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is the most important disease of scented rices in northeastern Haryana. In 1986 kharif, BI affected scented rices Pak, Basmati, T-3, and Basmati 370 grown on nearly 80,000 ha. Basmati occupying nearly 80% of the area was damaged most.

We surveyed 60 fields at the dough to maturity stage. Average neck BI incidence was 20-40% in Ambala, 30-70% in Karnal, and 30-80s in Kurukshetra. Incidence was highest under water stress and in late transplanted fields. □

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